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COMMUNITY-BASED SERVICE-LEARNING FOR FIRST SEMESTER ENGINEERING STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Community-based service-learning refers to the practice of combining learning outcomes in formal education with community service. The goal thereby is to make the educational outcomes and their achieving valuable not just for the learner, but also for his community. Unfortunately, service-learning remains underrepresented in engineering education today, while its potential in this domain is exceptionally high. In this paper, the context and outcomes of a community-based service-learning project for first semester engineering students are described. The project was implemented within a *Communication skills for engineers* course where students could complete a part of the course requirements by preparing a simple project using *mBot* educational robots and *micro:bit* boards, organizing the presentation of the project in an elementary school, and delivering a workshop for the pupils. Students' motivation, learning outcomes, and satisfaction with the project were investigated in order to help developing similar projects and increase students' voluntary participation. Research findings suggest that the project outcomes are beneficial for its stakeholders, and that the key motivators for students to take part in it are the importance of project results for others and practical work with technology.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Community-based service-learning

Community-based service-learning, sometimes also called *community-based learning* or *service-learning*, refers to the practice of combining meaningful community service with academic learning, personal growth, and civic responsibility [1]. This implies making the educational outcomes and their achieving in formal education valuable not just for the learner, but also for his community. Examples of service learning projects include the EPIC programme started at the Prude University [2], where students work on projects with local community organizations to help them those organizations in identifying and solving problems, or the Electrical & Electronic Engineering programmes within the College of Engineering and Informatics at the National University of Ireland [3], where service-learning even became an obligatory element of a four year study programme.

It is sometimes easy to confuse service learning with volunteering, internships, or project-based learning in general, yet volunteering does not imply a connection to improving learning outcomes, nor a connection to a course in formal education, while internships and project-based learning do not imply that the achieved results will have a positive impact on the community. Still, internships, project-based learning, and service-learning are all active learning approaches anchored in real contexts, which is associated with great improvements in achieving learning outcomes [4–6]. This does not come as a surprise, since problem solving, critical thinking, and reflection are inherent to those approaches [7].

Research has confirmed that service learning has a variety of positive effects on students including development of a sense of responsibility towards their community [8, 9], improvement of students' course-related learning outcomes [10], students' personal growth [11, 12], and improvements in students' problem solving skills [13]. In this paper, a project of including service-learning into a first-semester communication skills for engineers course is described. While very few such examples have been reported in the literature, such courses hold a great potential for service-learning due to their learning outcomes – the ability to efficiently communicate technical ideas and knowledge others.

1.2 Communication skills for engineers course

Communication skills for engineers or short *Communication skills* is an undergraduate level, first-semester, obligatory course at the University of Zagreb Faculty of Electrical Engineering and Computing. The course is worth 4 *European Credit Transfer System* points and every year approximately 670 students are enrolled in this course. The learning outcomes of the course include understanding and mastery of key media for communication of engineering professionals including e-mail, slideshows, resumes, writing, pitching, presentations, photography, and video. The course also includes topics like meetings, personalities and conflict resolving. Since the course is focused on learning outcomes that are very practical in their nature, there is an inherent problem with their acquisition and assessment in a

scalable way. Solving a multiple-choice quiz has only a limited value when the desired learning outcome is to prepare or at least introduce a student to holding a 60-second presentation or writing a formal email. Using authentic activities and their assessment, on the other hand, is impractical or impossible for large enrolment courses.

To help solving this issue while, at the same time, impacting and helping the community, a community-based service-learning project was introduced with help of the Institute for Youth Development and Innovativity (IYDI), a Croatia-based non-profit organization, on a project of STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) popularization [14]. Students' role in this partnership was to develop simple technical projects using *micro:bit* boards and *mBot* robots with help of their IYDI mentors, and to present those projects in workshops in elementary schools to encourage pupils' interest and familiarize them with the potential and practical aspects of some STEM-related topics.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Project description

For their individual projects, students could choose between *mBot* educational robots and *micro:bit* boards, or combine both. Students participated in a one-day workshop about those two technologies organized by IYDI after what they had two weeks to develop the topic for their project and have it approved by their IYDI mentors. By the end of the semester, students had to develop their individual projects, prepare digital learning materials based on which anyone interested could reproduce them (the developed materials would later be published on the IYDI website), find an elementary school in which they would present it to pupils in a workshop, and deliver the workshop typically in a 90-minute session. Based on the grades from their IYDI mentors, teachers, and pupils who participated in their workshop, students would be awarded credit for their final course project, as well as course credit for the presentation activity. The total value of those two course activities is 34% of overall course credit.

For IYDI, those students were a help in achieving their mission of popularizing the STEM field to elementary school pupils and increasing IYDI's outreach to elementary schools. Due to the decrease of general interest for STEM-related fields [2], this goal is considered particularly important. In context of the *Communication skills*' course, this project allowed students to practice their communication skills in the most authentic settings, by finding a school where they would present their work, doing all communication prior to their arrival, preparing the workshop, and, finally, delivering the workshop in front of an audience.

2.2 Data collection

After the project was finished in January 2020, data from students was collected in order to get feedback about students' experiences with this project, their motivation to participate in it, the learning outcomes, and their suggestions for improvements. Data was collected using an online questionnaire. A total of 19 students participated

in this project and 17 of them completed the online questionnaire. The questionnaire included students' identification number, yet it was available after their course grades has been finalized to encourage them to submit their honest opinions and not fear their answers would affect their course grade.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Survey results

3.1.1 Time cost of the project

It was assumed that the service-learning would be more time-consuming than the usual course activities of final project and pitch. Even though this could discourage students from participating, it was emphasized in the service-learning project presentation on the introductory course lecture. Survey results revealed that 7 of 17 students (41.18%) assumed, prior to starting it, that service-learning project would take them more time than the usual course project, the same number said that they weren't able to assess the time required for the project at that time, while 3 of them still assumed this would take them less time than alternative activities.

Students who, instead of the service-learning project, participated in the regular course activities reported at the end of the semester that they on average invested slightly less than 15 hours of work into their final projects, and slightly less than 5 hours of work into their pitches. On average, students who participated in the service-learning project reported a slightly higher workload compared to students who did not participate: 15 hours to develop their projects technically, 2 hours for communication with schools, 5.5 hours to prepare for a workshop, and 3 hours to travel to a school and deliver the presentation. On average, their workload was around 25.5 hours, which is 27.5% more than students not participating.

These results suggest students mostly did not assume the service-learning project would save them time compared to the usual course activities, and this still did not discourage them from applying. This is important since it was intended to include students who are motivated intrinsically in the project, and not those who find it opportunistic. The workload students reported in the project was still lower than it was expected, yet this is not important if the project goals are achieved.

3.1.2 Key motivating factors

The survey items regarding students' motivation first included a question if they had chosen to participate in the service-learning project because they liked it or because they disliked all other options available as the final Communication course's project. Only one student reported that this is the option he disliked least. Other 16 students were further asked what were the most important reasons that they wanted to participate the service-learning project. The answers to this were: because the project results are valuable for someone else (12/16, 75%), because it includes practical work with technology (10/16, 62.5%), because it includes teaching and delivering a workshop (9/16, 56.25%), because it includes working with other people (5/16, 31.25%), because it can be done in teams (5/16, 31.25%), and because it

seemed like less work to do (3/16, 18.75%). In line with those results, it seems that the two most important factors in this choice are that the project results are beneficial value for other society members, and that they include practical work with technology.

3.1.3 Learning outcomes (self-)evaluation

Students' learning outcomes were evaluated through their workshop quality, assessed by their audience, and the quality of the video and textual materials they developed for their project, assessed by their IYDI mentors. Workshop participants across all schools, both teachers and pupils, expressed their great satisfaction and submitted that as a textual statement to IYDI. The IYDI mentors additionally evaluated the quality of developed video and textual learning materials and students' engagement during the semester. Students were mostly very satisfied with their evaluations, and IYDI mentors with their works.

In the survey, students were, additionally asked to reflect on their learning during the project. On a scale from 1 (*very little*) to 4 (*a lot*) students on average reported that they learned about presenting their work to the public (3.24), delivering a group workshop (3.47), organizing an event and leading formal communication (3.41), developing digital learning materials (3.24). They assumed those were significantly higher than, for example, the advances in knowledge related to the technology they were using (2.82).

Overall, those results suggest students benefited from participating in this project. Some of the included activities and related learning are difficult to implement directly in the curriculum and are available only in context of this project, although they are directly related to the *Communication skills* course's outcomes.

3.1.4 Schools' feedback

Unfortunately, no feedback was acquired directly from schools where students held their workshops, and their feedback therefore remained anecdotal, based on what school staff would report back to IYDI mentors. The few recorded cases of schools reporting back were positive and suggested students managed to capture pupils' interest.

3.1.5 Proposed improvements

Some students suggested potential improvements and their comments were thematically related to improving coordination and support during the project, possibly by adding milestones or additional physical meetings (4/17), and to contact the school and learn about the prior knowledge of workshop participants at the beginning of the project, so that the topic can be better suited to them (2/17). Students reported that they would definitely (15/17, 88.2%) or possibly (2/17, 11.8%) recommend participating in this project to their younger colleagues next year, which was seen as another sign of their satisfaction, even with the higher project workload. Additionally, to assure workshops are suited to pupils' age and needs, mechanisms should be implemented to evaluate every workshop directly, in every school, after it

has been completed. Discouraging pupils' interest due to a badly prepared workshop would be the least desirable outcome, and to avoid it, good communication with schools and a direct feedback from their pupils would certainly be helpful. A survey to evaluate workshops aimed at pupils will be included in the next iteration of the project.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper reports on the first results of a community-based service-learning project in which computer and electrical engineering students within a Communication skills course helped a local non-profit organization to extend its outreach in popularizing and raising pupils' knowledge about some STEM-related topics. These results suggest this project is beneficial for all its stakeholders and that it helps students achieve course's learning outcomes. The importance of project results or other society members and practical work with technology are identified as key motivators for students to take part in it, while providing more guidance and technical help are identified as key potential improvements of the project. Follow-up implementation and research will focus on interventions to stimulate students' interest to participate in this project and formalize and better assess learning outcomes.

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